

Acetylacetonato (η^5 -indenyl)(η^5 -pyrrolyl)Zirconium(IV) Dithiocarbamates

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(η^5 -indenyl)(η^5 -pyrrolyl)zirconium(IV) dichloride, when treated with acetylacetonate in aqueous medium forms ionic derivatives of the type $[\text{RR}'\text{Zr}(\text{acac})]^+\text{Cl}^-$ ($\text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_7$, $\text{R}'=\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}$ and $\text{Hacac}=\text{acetylacetonate}$). These ionic derivatives react with dithiocarbamate anions in aqueous solution, giving ionic complexes of the general formula $[\text{RR}'\text{Zr}(\text{acac})]^+\text{dtc}^-$ ($\text{dtc}^- = \text{Me}_2\text{NCS}_2^-$, $\text{Et}_2\text{NCS}_2^-$, $i\text{-Pr}_2\text{NCS}_2^-$, Me , cyhxNCS_2^- , Et , cyhxNCS_2^- and $i\text{-Pr}$, cyhxNCS_2^-). IR and ^1H nmr studies demonstrate that the ligand acetylacetonate appears to be chelating in all these complexes. Consequently, tetrahedral coordination about the zirconium atom is proposed.

In earlier communications^{1,2}, we reported the synthesis of halogeno and complex halogeno anions as salts of oxinato (η^5 -indenyl)(η^5 -pyrrolyl)zirconium(IV) chelates, $[\text{RR}'\text{ZrL}]^+\text{X}^-$, where $\text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_7$, $\text{R}'=\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}$, L is the conjugate base of oxine and $\text{X}=\text{Br}^-$, I^- , $\text{ZnCl}_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}^-$, CdCl_4^{2-} or HgCl_3^- . In order to investigate whether the isolation of dithiocarbamate anions of acetylacetonato (η^5 -indenyl)(η^5 -pyrrolyl)zirconium(IV) is possible, we have studied the reaction of $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7)(\eta^5\text{-C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N})\text{Zr}(\text{acac})]^+\text{Cl}^-$ with dithiocarbamate anions in aqueous medium. The present paper describes the preparation and characterisation of a series of such ionic complexes.

Experimental

Nitrobenzene for conductance measurements was purified by the method of Fay *et al.*³. Sodium salts of dithiocarbamic acids were prepared by the method of Gilman and Blatt⁴. Indenyl thallium(I)⁵ and sodium pyrrolyl⁶ were prepared by the standard methods. $(\eta^5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7)\text{ZrCl}_3$ was prepared by the reaction of indenyl thallium(I) and zirconium tetrachloride in 1:1 molar ratio in THF. $(\eta^5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7)(\eta^5\text{-C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N})\text{ZrCl}_2$ was prepared by the interaction of $(\eta^5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7)\text{ZrCl}_3$ and sodium pyrrolide in THF in 1:1 molar ratio as described earlier².

Conductance measurements were made in nitrobenzene at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using an Elico Conductivity Bridge, Model CM-82. Solid state ir spectra were recorded in KBr pellets in the 4000-200 cm^{-1} region using a Perkin-Elmer 621 grating spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 at a sweep width of 900 Hz with a Perkin Elmer R-32 spectrometer. Chemical shifts are expressed relative to an internal reference of TMS (1% by volume).

Preparation of the complexes: An aqueous solution of $[\text{RR}'\text{ZrL}^+]\text{Cl}^-$ ($\text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_7$, $\text{R}'=\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}$; L is the conjugate base of acetylacetonate) was obtained by stirring an aqueous solution of $\text{RR}'\text{ZrCl}_2$ with

slight excess of acetylacetonate for 2 hr. Any resulting precipitate was removed by filtration. The filtrate was then added dropwise with shaking to a concentrated hot aqueous solution of appropriate sodium dithiocarbamate. The precipitate so obtained was digested on water bath at $60\text{-}70^\circ$ for 2 hr. It was filtered, washed with hot water and dried under vacuum. To remove any acetylacetonate impurity, the precipitates were dissolved in dichloromethane and reprecipitated by adding petroleum ether ($60\text{-}80^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

Table 1 lists the analytical data and physical characteristics of the dithiocarbamate salts, $[\text{RR}'\text{Zr}(\text{acac})]^+\text{dtc}^-$ ($\text{dtc}^- = \text{Me}_2\text{NCS}_2^-$, $\text{Et}_2\text{NCS}_2^-$, $i\text{-Pr}_2\text{NCS}_2^-$, Me , cyhxNCS_2^- , Et , cyhxNCS_2^- or $i\text{-Pr}$, cyhxNCS_2^-). The satisfactory elemental analyses support the stoichiometry assigned to these complexes. All the complexes are green in colour and moderately soluble in acetone, chloroform, benzene and nitrobenzene. They are thermally stable but decompose at higher temperatures without melting. Conductivity measurements reveal that the chelates are 1:1 electrolytes in nitrobenzene.

The assignments of ir bands have been made on the basis of published work. The appearance of a strong thioureide band near 1480 cm^{-1} supports the partial double bond character in $\text{S}_2\text{C}=\text{NRR}'$ bond, whereas, a band at $\sim 995\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the presence of $\text{C}=\text{S}$ bond⁷⁻⁹. The bands occurring around 1560 , 1530 and 475 cm^{-1} in the complexes may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ vibrations¹⁰, respectively.

The infrared spectra of the chelates show usual peaks for C_6H_5 group¹¹, viz., the C-H stretching frequency at $\sim 3080\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the perpendicular hydrogen wagging mode at $\sim 860\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the parallel hydrogen wagging vibration at $\sim 1030\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The bands owing to C-C stretching mode and ring breathing mode of

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF $[RR'Zr(acac)]^+dtc^-$ COMPLEXES

Complex	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Conductance* $M \times 10^3 = 0.5$	Analysis % ; Found (Calcd.)		
			Zr	N	S
1. $[RR'Zr(acac)]^+[Me_2NCS_2]^-$	192	29.8	18.32 (18.53)	5.46 (5.70)	13.22 (13.03)
2. $[RR'Zr(acac)]^+[Et_2NCS_2]^-$	197	30.2	17.38 (17.53)	5.12 (5.30)	12.18 (12.33)
3. $[RR'Zr(acac)]^+[i-Pr_2NCS_2]$	178-179	30.8	16.41 (16.63)	5.23 (5.11)	11.83 (11.70)
4. $[RR'Zr(acac)]^+[Me, cyhxNCS_2]^-$	167	29.2	16.01 (16.27)	5.12 (5.00)	11.21 (11.44)
5. $[RR'Zr(acac)]^+[Et, cyhxNCS_2]^-$	162-164	30.6	15.59 (15.88)	4.56 (4.88)	11.06 (11.16)
6. $[RR'Zr(acac)]^+[i-Pr, cyhxNCS_2]^-$	182	30.2	15.72 (15.50)	4.57 (4.77)	10.62 (10.90)

R = C₆H₇, R' = C₄H₄N* in ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹

the π -bond occur at ~ 1430 cm⁻¹ and ~ 1170 cm⁻¹, respectively. Besides these, the infrared spectra of all these compounds possess a medium intensity band at ~ 1120 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to $\nu(C-N-C)$ vibrations, indicative of pyrrolyl group. Further, the phenyl group of the indene is indicated by additional peaks at ~ 1340 cm⁻¹ (C-H stretching), ~ 1640 cm⁻¹ (C-C stretching), 760 cm⁻¹ (C-H out of plane bending) and ~ 700 cm⁻¹ (methylene rocking vibration)^{1,2}. Apart from this, an additional band at ~ 440 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to Zr-C₆H₅ vibrations^{1,3}.

The ¹H nmr spectra of the complexes show a singlet resonance at δ 4.70 and δ 5.70, which may be assigned to two pairs of equivalent protons of π -pyrrolyl ring (bonded to the α and β -carbon atoms relative to the nitrogen). The proton signals of this spectrum due to the π -pyrrolyl ring is very similar to the ¹H nmr spectra of $(\eta^5-C_4H_4N)Mn(CO)_3^+$ and $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)Fe(\eta^5-C_4H_4N)^{\delta,1,5}$. The resonance signals due to the C₆H₇ group were observed as a multiplet in the region δ 6.20-7.00 and δ 6.32-7.06, respectively.

The γ -proton (-CH=) resonance of the acetylacetonato group in the chelates occurs at lower field (δ 6.1-6.0 ppm) compared to the average values (δ 5.3 ppm) of several acetylacetonato complexes studied by Smith *et al*⁶. This is probably due, at least in part, to the net positive charge on the complex ion¹⁰. The δ values of methyl protons in the acetylacetonato moiety in the complexes is around 2.5 ppm and is also lower than the values reported for other acetylacetonato complexes. It may also be due to the cationic charge on the complex ion. The resonance signals of the alkyl and cyclohexyl groups in the dithiocarbamate moiety occur at almost the same frequency as for the free dithiocarbamate ligand.

Both the ir and ¹H nmr studies carried out for the present complexes indicate that the ligand acetyl-

acetone is chelating and the RR'Zr(IV)²⁺ moiety possess a wedge like sandwich structure with essentially tetrahedral coordination about the metal atom similar to that of dichlorides^{1,7}. Typical vibrational frequencies assigned to the dithiocarbamate moiety in the acetylacetonato chelates fully support the view that dithiocarbamate anion is a free anion.

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References

1. G. S. SODHI and N. K. KAUSHIK, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.*, 1981, **17**, 211.
2. G. S. SODHI and N. K. KAUSHIK, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1983, 152.
3. R. C. FAY and R. N. LOWRY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 1512.
4. H. GILMAN and A. H. BLATT, "Organic Synthesis", Collective Vol. I, John Wiley, New York, 1958, p. 448.
5. K. CHANDRA, R. K. SHARMA, A. K. GARG and B. S. GARG, *Chem. Ind.*, 1980, 537.
6. K. K. JOSHI, P. L. PAUSON, A. R. QAZI and W. H. STUBBS, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1964, **1**, 471.
7. J. CHATT, L. A. DUNCANSON and I. M. VENANZI, *Suomen Kemi*, 1956, **2**, B, 75.
8. B. F. G. JOHNSON, K. H. AL-ORAIDI and J. A. MCCLEVERTY, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1969, 1668.
9. F. BONATI and R. UGO, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1967, **10**, 257.

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10. J. P. FACKLER, JR., "Progress in Inorg. Chem.", 1966, **7**, 361.
11. H. P. FRITZ, "Advances in Organometallic Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1964, Vol. 1, p. 279.
12. G. W. H. SCHERF and R. K. BROWN, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1960, **38**, 697.
13. R. S. P. COUTTS and P. C. WALKER, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1975, **84**, 47.
14. K. K. JOSHI and P. L. PAUSON, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 326.
15. R. B. KING and M. B. BISNETT, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 796.
16. J. A. S. SMITH and J. D. THWAITES, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1962, **34**, 143.
17. N. V. ALEKSEEV and I. A. BONOVA, *Zh. Strukt. Khim.*, 1966, **7**, 103.